

NDAC/LO/080
1986, September 10

HIPPARCOS reductions for multiple stars, IVa.
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In the previous papers of this series, reduction methods for different types of double stars have been studied. The present note concerns multiples (3-5 components) with known a priori positions.

1. Simulation/solution for multiple stars

For simplicity, typical "trapezium"-systems are simulated, with separations in the range 1-30 arcsec and a single IFOV-pointing at the photocentre. The magnitudes are either all equal ($H=8.5$), or uniformly diminishing from $H=8.5$ to $H=11.5$ over the $n(=3-5)$ components. The proper motions are in different position-angles, but their absolute size is equal to twice the (common) parallax. Simulated IDT-counts and preprocessed Fourier coefficients are then obtained from the old SAMP-routine (cf. Paper I).

The solution program (MULSOL) differs from BISOL mainly in the number of unknowns. There are six parameters per component, (thus 30 in all for $n=5$), but their definition follows closely the $n=2$ case. The differential coefficients may be derived from eq. (I,12), and the formation and solution of the normal equations proceeds also as described in Paper I. (The weighting scheme of Paper Ib is used, with obvious modifications.)

2. Results

Results are available for six "series" ($n=3-5$, two magnitude distributions), with 10-20 completed runs in each. The a priori position errors were first taken to be 0.2 arcsec, but then about 30% of the $n=4$ and $n=5$ runs did not converge. (This is markedly "worse" than for $n=2$, cf. Paper II). With the a priori error at 0.1 arcsec, all runs do converge in 5-7 iterations. The other input data are as used before (position on the sky at latitude 32° ; $\sigma_F=2.5$; 4 slots observation time).

Table 1 shows the astrometric rms-values for equal-magnitude systems, with the $n=2$ entry taken from earlier runs (cf. Paper Ib). There is an expected error-increase with n , but the "total astrometric weight" $w_t (=n/\text{rms}^2)$ decreases only slightly after the initial drop from $n=2$ to $n=3$. (Note, however, that the actual weight of e.g. the photocentre may be slightly less because of possible correlations between the components.)

Table 1. Astrometric rms-errors (mas) and total weights for systems of n 8.5-magnitude stars within some 10 arcsec from each other.

n	2	3	4	5
rms	1.0	1.5	1.8	2.1
w_t	2.0	1.3	1.3	1.1

Table 2 gives corresponding rms-data with unequal magnitudes. Again the $n=2$ entries are from old runs (cf. Paper II). There is still a general increase of the errors with n , but the main factor that determines the astrometric accuracy is the star's magnitude. With the weight w_t now equal to Σrms^{-2} , the total weights are rather independent of both the number of components and their magnitude-distribution.

Table 2. Astrometric rms-errors (mas) and total weights for systems of n stars within some 20 arcsec from each other.

H	n	2	2	3	4	5
8.5		0.9	0.8	0.9	1.0	1.1
9.25/9.5					2.7	2.8
10.0		3.2		3.8		5.7
10.50/10.75					7.4	10
11.5			12	16	16	21
w_t		1.3	1.6	1.3	1.2	1.0

Another interesting parameter is the "error increase factor" f_e (see Paper II), measuring how the actual errors relate to the formal errors given by the LS-solution. For $n=3-5$, the f_e -values are found to be nearly independent of magnitude and of n . A grand mean over all the present runs gives $f_e=1.2$, in close agreement with the binary results given in Paper II.

3. Conclusions

For the rather trivial case of a multiple star with known a priori information, the present tests show that astrometric data may be obtained for all its components. The accuracy is somewhat degraded as compared with a double star configuration, but not seriously so. The tests have been for $n \leq 5$, but there is no reason why $n=6-7$ should behave differently. Also, there should be no difficulty with a 2-position IFOV pointing (e.g for a "double double" configuration).

A more important question is to what extent it is possible to discover and obtain data for an unknown third component to a known double star. This will be the subject of the future report IVb.